

ASSESSMENT OF PATIENTS RESPONSES TOWARDS CRM PRACTICES

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Abstract:

The present study is an attempt to evaluate the CRM practices critically in health care sector. Health care industry is growing day-by-day in India. The numbers of patients are growing rapidly due to somany reasons. Keeping this point in view the researcher has made an attempt to assess the patient's responses towards the CRM practices. The data has been collected, tabulated and further statistical tools like Chi-Square test, Correlation, ANOVA etc., have been used to analyze the data.

Key Words: CRM Practices, Patients, Perception, Doctors & Health Care

Introduction:

Health is a fundamental human right and a world wide social goal Health is necessary for the realization of basic human needs and to attain the status of a better quality of life In 1977, the 30th World Health Assembly decided that the main social target of governments and World Health Organization (WHO) in the coming decades should be " the attainment by all the citizens of the world by the year 2000 of a level of health that will permit them to lead a socially and economically productive life" (WHO 1979).

Such a declaration has led most of the governments in western countries to give much more priority to their health care systems through higher allocation and better utilization of resources in order to improve the quality of health care Less developed countries are in the process of improving it and some among them are yet to start India also has been attempting towards this end The major hindrances on its way could be attributed to inadequate allocation of resources for the health sector, rapid population growth, inefficient use of the resources allocated and above all lack of public consciousness about their own health status Health being a State subject in the Indian federal system, different states in the country have been trying to meet the WHO health goal through mobilization of both internal and external resources including the funds from foreign agencies Specifically, the state of Andhra Pradesh has been in the forefront in this regard and somewhat successful in developing a better public health care delivery system. However, the achievement of the goal of "health for all" for the state is perhaps still a distant dream Here a major point that needs to be understood is that the country needs to give emphasis on the rural health services where nearly 70% of total Indian Population still lives. Despite repeated pronouncements by the policy makers about the need for rural emphasis, health services provided to the people have continued to be urban oriented where a major chunk of the resources allocated to the health sector are spent In this chapter we attempt to give an outline of the functioning of the health care delivery system of India in general and Andhra Pradesh in particular Before going into detailed debate on the issues involved it may be useful to clarify certain basic concepts that are frequently used in health care research.

Review of Literature:

Lien, Wu, Chen, and Wang (2014), examined the effect of service quality on trust. The study findings revealed that interaction quality and outcome quality positively influenced patients' trust in the original hospital. The study also concluded that trust in the original hospital and its allied hospitals positively influenced patients' willingness to recommend the allied hospitals.

Ehsan (2015) assessed the service quality of hospital outpatients' departments from the patients' perspective. The study found that physician consultation, information provided to the patient, and the physical environments of the clinic were the factors determining quality of outpatient services.

Ehsan, Z. (2015), Service Quality of Hospital Outpatient Department: Patients' Perspective. *International Journal of Health Care Quality Assurance*, 28 (8), pp. 778 – 790.

V.K.Moorthy, P.Karthikeyan & N.Prakash (2016), examined the Relationship between Service Quality and Patients' Satisfaction in the Hospital Industry. The study indentified five important dimensions of hospital service quality. These are, Clinical Care, Admission Procedure, Reliability, Trust and Infrastructure. The study reveals that there is a significant impact of the above five dimensions on patient satisfaction. Furthermore, the highly perceived hospital service quality dimensions among the patients are Trust and Clinical Care.

Hall M.C, Elliot K.M., Stiles G.W. (2003) paper investigates the correlates, dimensionality, and determinants of patient satisfaction in the hospital health care encounter. All of the individual hospital characteristics assessed were found to be significantly related to patient satisfaction. The findings suggest that patients evaluate hospital service quality along four distinct dimensions. The relative importance of these four factors in predicting overall satisfaction, in descending order, is: (1) physician/ capabilities, (2) nurses/ staff, (3) amenities, and (4) accessibility. In combination, these four factors explain 63 percent of overall patient satisfaction.

Frank Tidikis and Leann Strasen study on the patient care units improve service and financial outcomes. Because of Delray Community Hospital's success with the PFCUs, (Patient-focused care units) the hospital corporation is initiating PFCUs in other facilities. Each facility has unique characteristics that require modifications of the overall PFCU model.

Patient-focused care units have reduced labour costs for a 211 - bed for-profit acute care hospital and improved patient and physician satisfaction by reducing the number of hospital staff members who interact with patients. They also have enhanced efficient resource use by relocating to the patient care site 75 percent of the labour, supply, and technology resources needed by patients. The researchers stressed the importance of staff education, cross training, communication, financial supporting and labour productivity systems. They concluded that each facility has unique characteristics that require modifications. These modifications definitely assist the patient's focussed care units with the help of hospital staff. The time needed for staff education and cross-training was initially underestimated but quickly adjusted after the first unit became operational. In particular, more intensive communication with employees was needed to prepare them for change than initially anticipated. Additional communication was necessary to describe the external forces that dictated a change in the deliver system. The goal was to create a mind-set that emphasized the increase in fixed payment business, the rate of escalation of hospital costs, and the need to improve productivity in all units of the hospital.

Ratnaja Gohula and Madavi Garikaparathi (2003) study on the CRM in service sector-focus of customer Relationship Management-Need to Look Beyond the Customer - Referral to Hospital Service", The researchers observed that any CRM effort should logically begin from the supplier of inputs for the product, move onto operations and production personnel, then to the distribution and finally end with the customer. The study concluded that hospital service providers should develop a strong and positive relationship with the supplier of input even if they have to pay a premium for it followed by a process relationship management resulting in customer loyalty retention.

Jasleen Kaur and Gurudeep Singh (2004) article on Marketing of Hospital. The researcher focused on strategies for promoting hospital services such as separate department for marketing, effective customer relationship management, designing functional logo, developing linkages with patients, participating in conferences, and seminars, target corporate sector, tie-up with health insurance companies, professional sales promotion, specialized schemes, quality assurance from independent agencies and maintaining and updating the websites etc., The author pointed out that the success of any organisation in future is directly linked with the type and quality of marketing activities it undertakes.

In the article "Health Care in India: Opportunities and Challenges" by Babu, T. D. and Jayabal, G. (2004). The authors discussed as to how to build up health care as a global industry. Further, they highlighted health care sector in India, challenges and opportunities for the health care sector in India and the strategies recommended to make the hospitals global. According to them the hospital should improve the infrastructure status and modify the rate structure.

Mohammad Faisal Khan & Humera Khan (2004) study on the quality Management in the Health Care Industry. The researchers focussed on the ever rising expectations of the consumer in the present health care industry's scenario. The researchers stated that a quality management system consists of three main elements such as

- ✓ The introduction of indicators for the assessment of quality and setting of standards in the local practice;
- ✓ The development of software to simplify the collection of data and the computerized medical records;
- ✓ The quality management system required in hospitals, which will evaluate input process and the output of each sub-system in the organisation to satisfy the needs of the clientele.

Gaby Odekerken - Schroder and Josee Bloemer (2004) study on "Constraints and Dedication, as a Driver for Relationship commitment: An Empirical Study in a Health Care context". The researcher empirically determined the role of the service providers on relationship commitment. The major results of this study showed that dedication is strongly influenced by trust, which in turn is determined by satisfaction.

Munesh Raj Lakhey (2004) study on the Globalisation and Trade Opportunities in Health Services. He assessed the importance of health service trade in the global era, changing background of trade, structure of services trade, opportunities for developing countries, outsourcing of services, information based services, foreign direct investments and management perspectives. He suggested that the quality and cost/ comparative advantages alone are of not much help when we compete freely with the World. In fact competent management innovation and successful marketing are equally important.

Srinivasan, R. (2004) study carried on Health Care Service Marketing. The researcher discussed the functions and systems of hospital and medical transcription services. He suggested improving the infrastructure to get success in medical transcription.

Results and Discussion:

- ✓ Record management of a particular patient is very important in every hospital, but this kind of policy is not followed in somany hospitals today properly. Hence it is suggested that it is better to mainatian a

record for each and every patient in a chronological manner which projects the health condition of the patient in order to give proper treatment and medicines as and when necessary.

- ✓ Disposal of waste is very important in the hospital otherwise it leads to spoil the health of the others. The hospital management is responsible to look after the disposal of infectious materials like expired medicines, Cotton etc.
- ✓ Numerous specialists are available in the hospitals. The flow of patients is also increasing day-by-day. The management has to keep this in their mind and they have to prepare a proper schedule to the Doctors and Patients in order to serve them in a better manner.
- ✓ Another important aspect is grievance handling. It is quite common to face the problems by the patients those who visited the big hospitals. So that the hospital management should maintain a complaint register in order to resolve the problems faced by the patients.

Conclusion:

CRM is playing a crucial role in Indian health care sector. Technology, organizational culture and support from top level management will enhance the performance in health care sector. CRM strategies will also be helpful in improving the profitability of the organization, because in order to satisfy the healthcare consumers, providers should concentrate on courtesy and efficiency. Patients' gratification is more important to maintain longterm relationship.

Pointer for Future Research:

The results of the research work contain substantial implications for hospital administrators. The outcome of the study facilitates the managers to determine priorities of patients. The present case study can also be used as a device for the hospital administrators' in order to identify a variety of dimensions of CRM practices wherever improvements are considered necessary to enhance the patients' satisfaction levels. The current study considered patient's perception towards CRM practices in SVIMs hospital and further research should examine the: relationship between hospital service quality and patient's retention, comparison of CRM practices of multi-speciality hospitals & government hospitals and employees' perceptions towards CRM practices and its outcomes on hospital performance.

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